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Universal Brotherhood of mankind

-Assignment on Sikhism

-By Savio Saldanha SJ

“The One Light is the light in all bodies.”

“The One Light is all pervading, only a few know it.”

I. Abstract:

The above quotes are taken from the sayings of Guru Nanak, and form the *Naam Jappu* of the Sikhs (Ang 120 and 124). I was fortunate to have several Sikh companions in school and in my office, and also had the chance to visit a Gurudwara and even did a turn of *Seva*, with my friend. Which is a kind of penance through service, we kept and cleaned the footwear of the devotees to the Gurudwara as a part of our *Seva*, and it was an amazing experience. I also had food in the langar (community kitchen) which serves hot meals to everyone, for free. This and other experiences have made me hold Sikhism in high reverence. In this paper, I have selected the tenet of Universal Brotherhood (*Sarbat Da Bhala*), which I have been fascinated with since the beginning.

II. Introduction:

‘The Fatherhood of God and the Brotherhood of men’ is one of the basic tenets of Sikhism. The Sikhs believe in monotheism, like the Abrahamic religions. However unlike Christianity, they do not believe in a Trinitarian God, but in ‘*Ik Onkar*’ (The Formless One). Let us consider their *Mul Mantra* (Basic Mantra): ‘*Ik Omkar sati namu karata purakhu, nirbhau nirvairu akal murati ajuni saibhan gur prasadi*’, which translated means, ‘**There is but One God. He is all that is. He is the Creator of all things and He is All-pervasive. He is without fear and without enmity. He is the Enlightener and can be realised by the grace of Himself alone**’. As God is One Formless and Omniscient, He is present in everyone. This unites the entire mankind into One Universal Brotherhood.

III. Universal Brotherhood:

A) Spiritual Perspective:

Let us look at how this tenet of Universal Brotherhood is included in the very Spirituality (Soul) of Sikhism. The Sikhs are bound to pray aloud twice a day in the words:

“O God, in Your Name, shower Your blessings on everyone.”

In other words, Sikhs pray not only for themselves alone but also for the entire humanity. This belief in the oneness of humanity, and the insistence on working for the welfare of all people, whether Sikhs or not, even at the cost of sacrificing one’s life, is what sets Sikhism as a unique form of religion. Sikhs are expected to treat all people with equal respect, irrespective of their religion, caste or nationality.

The Sikhs are men of prayer. They believe in goodness of humanity. They wish welfare of humanity as a whole during their prayer normally offered twice a day. They pray for universal peace, prosperity and protection of human beings over this universe.

- *“God’s glory ever increases; in His Will, Nanak prays for the good of everyone.”*

(Ardas-Sikh Prayer)

It is how the daily prayer of the Sikhs ends. Thus, they pray for everyone in the beginning of the prayer and conclude it in a similar manner. The Sikhs like to share an example of a certain Bhai Kanhaiya who used to pour water in every body's mouth in the battle field irrespective of the religion of the fighting soldier, thus, implying that they care for every soul, even if it is of the enemy on a battlefield.

- Guru Nanak Dev said,

“Within every one is the soul and the soul is God Himself who pervades all and everywhere.”

Thus, he clearly told his followers that every person has within himself the Real Presence of God, and so everyone should be treated with the same respect and dignity, one would bestow on God.

- Guru Nanak Dev further said,

“Let universal brotherhood be the highest aspiration of your religious order.”

Thus, Guru Nanak Dev gave his followers a hierarchy in the tenets that they should always consider, Universal Brotherhood to be of utmost importance and preference in Sikhism.

- Guru Arjan Dev said,

“None is my enemy and I an enemy to none. No one is stranger to me and I am friend of all.”

He thus, spoke of universal connectedness, the Divine presence which binds the entire humanity into one. Guru Arjan Dev was also a warrior guru, he fought numerous battles against the mughals, but it is recorded as how he gave honourable burial to the slain enemy soldiers, and made provisions for the treatment of all the injured, irrespective of they being friend or foe.

- Guru Arjan Dev said,

“I have befriended all and unto everyone, I am a friend.”

This statement shows the spiritual depth of the Sikh guru, who felt connected to the entire humanity rising above the petty differences.

- The Sikhs daily prayer includes the following verse:

‘Nanak Nam Charhdi Kala, Tere Bhane Sarbat Da Bhala’, which means Supreme is the Word of God, May God bless every human being.

Thus, we see that the tenet of Universal Brotherhood is among the most important ones in Sikhism. It can also be said as to contain the very essence of Sikh Spirituality and is the foundation block of its philosophy.

B) Practical Interpretations and Applications:

Considering the above prayer verses and the sayings (*Gurmukhi*) of Sikhism, a Sikh is expected to conduct himself/herself in the following manner, with regards to the Universal Brotherhood: The Sikh must lead a harmonious life, within himself as well as those around him. He must stand for human liberty, equality and fraternity. Here another tenet must be mentioned here despite it not being immediately related to our topic, *‘Na zulam karo, na zulam saho’*, which means do not be an oppressor, neither

tolerate oppression. This tenet also asks the Sikhs to stand for freedom of belief, worship, religious tolerance and peaceful co-existence. A Sikh must stand for universal peace and prosperity.

Before the advent of Guru Nanak Dev, the society in India was routinely and systematically flouting human freedom and equality. There was a rigid caste system of power and privilege for high caste and men. The women were relegated to second class status, just above cattle and crops. They were dependent on goodwill of men. A woman's life was of home and hearth, bedroom and kitchen. Her only goal was to marry, bear and raise children. She was to find fulfillment of her life through the achievements of her husband and offspring. She did not have an independent identity of her own, and was known in relation to her male relatives (very much like the women in Israel, during the times of Jesus).

Guru Nanak Dev revolted against this injustice. So we can say, in a way that Sikhism was an extension of Sramana movements of the ancient times. Resultantly, Sikhism does not teach discrimination on the basis of caste, color, creed or gender. It strives for liberty, equality and fraternity. Its goal is equality of lowest with highest, men with woman and equality of human beings. It believes in social, economic, political and religious freedom on equality basis. Sikhism thus, preaches that all human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights. When Guru Gobind Singh, ordained the 'Khalsa' or the 'Pure', he gave uniformity to the socio-cultural presence of a new order of humanity. He designated all the men of the 'Khalsa' collectively to be a 'Singh' or 'Lion' and all the women to be a **'Kaur' or a 'princess'**. This concept of being Kaur was the symbolized liberation from the inherent traditional hierarchies that bound women. It was a declaration that women were not below or subordinate to the men. 'Kaur' is the equalizer a name that all Sikh women carry giving them the identity of princess who had the world as their inheritance. Sikhism as a religion never discriminated against the women going through the lunar cycle of menstruation. They were not considered impure, as in Hinduism. They were given free entry to temples, kitchens and sacred places. Guru Gobind Singh also taught women the art of warfare. This is very important, the idea of universal brotherhood which includes women, was far ahead of its times. Thus we see, Sikhism actually took the idea that the spirit of God dwelling in all humans very seriously and strove to bring about changes which were radical in appearance. For this they incurred the wrath and scorn of upper caste Hindus.

It has been explained in the discussion of the spiritual aspects of universal brotherhood that Sikhs are expected to respect all persons. People may appear different because of their language, color, social habits but these variations are superficial and the result of different cultures and climates. Internally, Sikhism believes that we all have the same spirit. They explain it beautifully with the following example, just as gold can be made into ornaments of different designs but it remains gold, so people's outward appearances can be different but still they remain human beings created by the same God.

These high expected moral standards transcend to a good moral life for the adherents of Sikhism. For Sikhs, as for the followers of many other faiths, lying, cheating, stealing etc. is forbidden. Sexual relations are restricted to married couples only. Thus, it seeks to preserve the dignity of human beings and the sanctity of marriage. Recognizing that during the medieval ages, after battle women of the defeated side were often raped as an expression of power over the enemy, Guru Gobind Singh ordered that any person guilty of rape would be expelled from the Khalsa Panth. The moral character of Sikhs, in war and in peace, was praised highly even by the Muslim historians of those times. This fact is astounding because Sikhism was in a constant state of war with the invading armies of Muslims and a war of words with the puritans of Hinduism. Despite all this the successive gurus were able to maintain the highest forms of morality and added values and principles which enhanced the moral life of the people following Sikhism.

IV. Similarities with other religions:

I am reminded of a Sanskrit shloka from Upanishad, '*sarve bhavantu sukhinah, sarve santu niramayah, sarve bhadrani pasyantu ma kascid duhkha bhagbhavet*', which means 'May all people be happy, free from illnesses. May all see what is auspicious, and may no one suffer'. This prayer is often recited since olden times for the wellbeing of humanity; it has gained a renewed significance especially during these pandemic times. It also resonates with the same universal brotherhood aspect which is preached in the Sikhism. An Upanishadic hymn says '*Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam*' - which means that the whole world is one single family. This is considered as an integral part of the Hindu Philosophy. Hence, language and religion should never be a reason for discriminating against people based on any differences.

The Quran says: "*O mankind, indeed We have created you from male and female, and have made you into nations and tribes, that you may know one another. Indeed the most honored of you in the sight of Allah is the most righteous. Indeed, Allah is Knowing and Acquainted*" (Quran 49:13) The holy Quran says: "*whoever kills a human being without any reason manslaughter or corruption on earth, it is though he had killed all mankind*" (Quran 5:32). In other verses, the Quran states "*Do not kill souls which Allah has made sacred except to the due process of Allah*" (Quran 6:151). We thus see the aspects of Universal Brotherhood and equality of human beings are fundamental philosophy of Islam. Islam has always encouraged its followers to live with tolerance, harmony, love, brotherhood and peace on the earth adding that humanity is more precious than any of the religions. God has granted human dignity to all mankind. Islam also asserts that no nation is created to be above other nations, rather the differences of region, religion, colour, and gender makes no difference of man's worth in the eyes of Allah, rather his good deeds and obedience to the Will of Allah is what makes the difference.

The Holy Bible clearly mentions the tenet of Universal Brotherhood several times. In the Gospel according to Mark, Jesus clearly tells his followers that, '*Whoever does God's will is my brother and sister and mother.*' (Mark 3:35). He thus implies that everyone is a child of God irrespective of race, gender and other differences, if only he/she does what is right in the eyes of God. In the very first book of the Holy Bible, Genesis (Gen.1:27), it is mentioned '*So God created humankind in His image*', further in the Acts of the Apostles (Acts 17:26) it is mentioned that '*From one ancestor he made all nations to inhabit the whole world*', thus the Holy Bible underlines the union of all humanity as originating from one ancestor, and created by the same Creator and in His sacred image. To further strengthen the bond, Saint Paul in his first letter to the Corinthians (1Cor.6:19) asks '*Do you not know your body is the temple of the Holy Spirit.*', thus confirming as Sikhism, that humanity is not only bound by a physical bond of shared ancestry, but also a strong spiritual bond. The same Holy Spirit of God dwells in every human being, irrespective of his religion, race, caste or gender.

The three major religions in the world, Christianity, Islam and Hinduism preach Universal Brotherhood and bring out the fact that the entire humanity is bound together through God who is the Creator of all things seen and unseen as well as a deep spiritual bond of the dwelling of the Spirit of God in everyone which connects it together. Then there have been saints in all religions like St. Francis of Assisi in Christianity, the Sufi saints in Islam, Sai baba of Shirdi, and many others who have raised the bar on Universal Brotherhood to include also the nature, and planetary bodies like the sun and the moon.

In the tribal cultures around the world, be it in the several tribes of India as well as the Native American tribes, the feeling of a Universal Brotherhood was ingrained deeply. They worshipped the Nature as The Great Spirit to whom all the spirits of the world moved. Their reference to the earth as the Mother, and the fruits and vegetables which grow in the nature as her gifts to humanity proves a

sophisticated and deep entrenched philosophy albeit an unwritten and unorganised existed, passed in the form of oral traditions, generation to generation.

V. My Insights:

The tenet of Universal Brotherhood is very interesting as it enforces the common belief that the Spirit of God is alive in everyone irrespective of any differences. The Hindu belief of Vasudaiva Kuumbakam, 'the world is my home' was also spoken on the other side of the world by Jerome Nadal when he said, 'el mundo es nuestra casa'. The deep bonds of connection between people become evident when a loved one is sick and you feel that something is not right and call him/her only to find out the reason for your unknown discomfort. This inbuilt feeling of brotherhood makes people rush to the aid of a stranger who has met with some sort of accident. It is also this feeling of Universal Brotherhood which makes you seethe with helpless anger and emotion on seeing the farmers being crushed to death in Uttar Pradesh, the terrorized people of Syria, Afghanistan and other parts of the world. This is the same feeling which makes you help an unknown person or a child in distress and the immeasurable joy you get when they return your effort with a simple smile.

We see the great thinkers and the people of old, who were very much connected to the realm of spirituality, had spoken of the Universal Brotherhood, even though they were separated by distance and time. And whenever humanity seemed to forget this, there always came along a so called 'crazy' person who seemed to remind us of this long forgotten yet cherished ideal of our ancestors.

We see this ideal being practiced till now by the so called 'illiterate and unsophisticated' farmers, who after returning from his field, although tired, washes and cleans his bullocks who have helped him in ploughing the field, he then proceeds to feed them lovingly and only then proceeds with his personal bath and other ablutions. This act of extending the Universal Brotherhood beyond humans to all the animals and even the vegetation is another beautiful act of gratitude to our Creator, acknowledging His presence not only in humans but in all of His creation. This is what made Guru Nanak to proclaim that the Universal Brotherhood was the highest aspiration of the Sikh religious order.

At the same time, we also see the distress and turmoil being caused in the world where humanity has lost its touch with this ideal. There seems to be a force of division which thrives on exclusivity and elitism which is inimical to the ideal of universality. The people, who advocate supremacy on the basis of religion and caste, are somehow proving to be obstacles to the very teachings of the faith they think they are upholding.

In the conclusion, I would like to add that the tenet of Universal Brotherhood is a value which unites all humanity into one family of being God's children, irrespective of religion, region, caste or gender. It should be propagated to bring about the peace, equality, fraternity and liberty which the humanity is craving for. Dalai Lama, Pope Francis are two religious leaders of a great standing and goodwill throughout the world and seem to be propagating Universal Brotherhood, they should be supported in their endeavors by all the people of goodwill. ***Sarbat Da Bhala.***

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